

Interplay between Conflict Resolution and ChatGPT: A Review of Selected Literature

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Abstract

Efforts are being made to resolve conflicts that are inevitable in the world. Technology has taken centre stage in transforming the world and in the ways that people relate together. Since its invention, Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a technological tool and one of its offshoots, ChatGPT, have started influencing the ways conflicts are being resolved, especially in achieving Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (SDGs) that has to do with peaceful coexistence by the year 2030. While there is robust scholarly literature on conflict resolution, being an emerging trend, there is meagre scholarly literature on ChatGPT as an AI tool. Therefore, this paper aims to review some selected literature on the interplay between ChatGPT (as an AI tool) and conflict resolution and come up with some recommendations on how the two concepts can relate together as people aspire to achieve the aforementioned SDG Goal. The paper reviewed what scholars and other stakeholders have said about concepts like conflicts, conflict resolution, AI, and ChatGPT, and the nexus between these concepts. The paper concluded with a recommendation that experts, scholars, and other stakeholders in peace study and conflict resolution should harness the opportunities that ChatGPT offers in their operations to achieve Goal 16 of the SDGs by the year 2030.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), ChatGPT, conflict resolution, conflicts, Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, peacebuilding

Introduction

The world is full of conflicts of many kinds. These conflicts include conflicts within oneself, interpersonal conflicts, conflicts within a nation, and above all, international conflicts. Conflicts like marital conflicts, conflicts in churches, and between churches, and inter-faith conflicts are other conflicts that faith-based organizations are also contending with every day. Against the backdrop that the major roots of conflicts are closely connected to the “question of unsustainable development” (Otokola, 2016, p. 70). These conflicts have to be discussed and resolved to have a peaceful and non-violent society. So, to achieve Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations that has to do with “peaceful and inclusive societies” (The United Nations, n.d.). This has to do with peacebuilding in particular and conflict resolution in general which have been regarded by someone as “some of humanity’s most needed but toughest endeavours” (Verdict, 2023).

As observed by Lillard (2010) the modern world has metamorphosed from an analog world to a digital world where digitalization has influenced and continues to influence many old-style establishments. In this digital world, technological tools play significant roles, and the emergence of social media has tremendously changed the ways people communicate throughout the world (Tella & Ampofo, 2016; Deng & Lin, 2022). Bognár (2019) presented a paper at a conference highlighting the impacts of technology on conflict resolution in general. Besides, the advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in general and one of its tools, ChatGPT, in

particular, has transformed communication among people to take a dramatic turn (Deen, 2023). This was corroborated by Limna, et al. (2023, p. 65) who opined, "In the digital era, technology is increasingly developing and provides convenience for various aspects of life...."

Deng & Lin (2022) identified machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing as parts of several types of Artificial Intelligence (AI). There are many AI technologies or tools like ChatGPT, "Google Bard, Microsoft Bing AI and many more" (Learn about Chat GPT, 2023). However, this paper aims to review some selected literature on the interplay between the AI tool – ChatGPT – and conflict resolution and come up with some recommendations on how the two concepts can relate together as people aspire to achieve Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations that has to do with peaceful coexistence in society by the year 2030. While there is robust scholarly literature on conflict resolution, there is meagre scholarly literature on ChatGPT as an AI tool is an emerging trend. Scholars are just beaming their searching light on the cutting-edge AI chatbot technology.

Conflict

To give an accurate definition of conflict is difficult. The reason is that conflict is diverse and it is contingent upon the context or usage of the word conflict. This has made peace researchers disagree on the meaning of the concept of conflict. However, Ishaka & Ogbanje (2018) gave an etymological background to the word "conflict". The two scholars asserted that the word originated from "a Latin word called *confligere*, which means to clash or to engage in a fight or a battle over certain things, goals, or values" (Ishaka & Ogbanje, 2018, p. 4). This Latin word "...connotes a confrontation between one or more parties aspiring towards incompatible or competitive means or ends" (Dajwan, 2021). Many scholars prefer to describe conflict with scenarios rather than simply define it. Therefore, Pia & Diez (n.d., p. 2) described a conflict as "a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals." Ifezue (2021, p. 351) regarded conflict "as state of disharmony or disagreement between two or more oppositions which can arise in any social institution, religion inclusive." Ngwoke & Ituma (2020, p. 3) rather described conflict from its causes as "a disagreement, controversy or quarrel between two or more people or groups of people." As a conflict (apart from intrapersonal conflict) has been identified as something that happens between parties, these parties according to Anumve, Fada, & Igah (2020, p. 146) could be "individuals, groups, communities or state...." Viewing conflict as something that is "inextricable" in any relationship, Steen & Shinkai (2020, p. 51) described conflict as "an interactive state in which the behaviors or goals of one actor are at some degree incompatible with the behaviors or goals of some other actor or actors." A faith-based relief services manual has a similar definition of conflict: "disagreement or struggle between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values or goals" (Catholic Relief Services, 2018, p. 16). To Ebegbulem (2012, p. 17), conflict is viewed as "an inevitable product of cohabitation or co-existence of individuals or people in society struggling for limited values or resources as against countless desires."

This researcher would prefer this definition of conflict by Galtung (1973): "the condition under which there are actors in pursuit, and-or defense, of incompatible goals." This definition is preferred against the backdrop of another similar definition of conflict by Folarin & Adedokun (2016) with an analysis. The definition is: "a disagreement through which the parties involved perceive a threat to their needs, interests or concerns" (Folarin & Adedokun, 2016). Its analysis is: one, conflict is a disagreement; two, parties are involved in any conflict (except

intrapersonal conflicts); three, the threat is perceived in the conflict; and four, needs, interests, or concerns are involved in the conflict (Folarin & Adedokun, 2016). As highlighted by Käihkö (2020), conflict usually involves the use of force or violence, the creation of a rift in relations between the conflicting parties, and possibly high risks or dangers at the end of the day. Bello & Abdullahi (2021, p. 2) recently defined conflict, in relation to peace, as “the inability of people to sustain and maintain peaceful and harmonious coexistence during social interactions.”

Conflict can emerge at any time. Conflict is normal. It is unavoidable. Nietz (2018, p.15) opined that conflict is “an inherent part of human nature.” For Asogwa & Okeke (2021, p. 411), conflict is “a phenomenon that is an important part of human existence and a natural part of our daily lives.” As noted by Folarin & Adedokun (2016), “Conflicts are becoming more common, complex, and destructive with no single approach appearing, currently, to be working effectively.” Similarly, in the words of Ekpo (2019, p. 76), “Conflicts do not just emerge *ex nihilo*. For every conflict situation, there is always a political, economic and socio-cultural context upon which such conflict manifests and hitches.”

Ubandawaki (2020, p. 175) has asserted that conflict “is a social phenomenon interwoven with other social institutions like politics, economy, religion, and culture of a given society.” Despite this assertion and the fact that Cloke (2004, p. 220) viewed a conflict as “both a creative and a destructive force” or “ethically neutral” as Schliesser (2020, p. 2) put it, and Ishaka & Ogbanje (2018, p. 4) opined that “conflict serves as an indicator of change or the need for change,” yet many scholars view conflict as something that always brings negative or bad results. Many scholars with this opinion identified conflict with its multidimensional consequences as “an obstacle to progress, economic growth, political stability and overall socio-economic development” (Ngwoke & Ituma, 2020, p. 3). Nevertheless, while conflict, as described by Chaudhary (2021, p. 924), is “inevitable and a latent reality present in every culture,” Pasricha (2020, p. 115) asserted that conflicts “are neither positive nor negative, neither inevitable nor necessarily disastrous in their consequences.” Against the backdrop that “the degree, approach, and skills in handling conflict ... vary from person to person” (Arikewuyo, et al., 2020, p. 3), the handling of a conflict situation will determine its outcome, whether positive or negative. A conflict that is constructively and peacefully dealt with will likely bring positive transformation, while a conflict that is dealt with violently will likely bring negative consequences (Abdalla & Sender, 2019).

Conflict Resolution

The term conflict resolution became prominent in the last two decades when the Cold War ended and many civil wars started in eastern and southern Europe and many conflicts in Africa made scholars and analysts elucidate the shifting nature of war and how to end it (Carayannis, et al., 2014, p. 6). Alade (2020, p. 112) opined, “Conflicts are resolved when both conflicting parties are satisfied with the outcome of the resolution in terms of their basic needs being met and all fear dismantled.” In corroboration of this simple definition of conflict resolution, Katumba (2021, p. 2) was of the opinion that “the concept of conflict resolution can be thought to encompass the use of nonviolent resistance measures by conflicted parties in an attempt to promote effective resolution.” So, one can sum the focus of conflict resolution on “the deep-rooted causes of conflict, including structural, behavioral, and above all, attitudinal aspects” (Ilo, 2015, p. 100) or simply, in the words of Sihotang (2021, p. 277), “to achieve or promote peace.”

Conflict resolution – also known, according to Katumba (2021, p. 2), as “reconciliation” and “dispute resolution” – has to do with all the procedure that aims at tackling the fundamental causes of direct, cultural, and structural violence (Wani, Suwitra, & Fayeye, 2013). This process ranges “from negotiation to diplomacy, from mediation to arbitration, from facilitation to adjudication, from conciliation to conflict prevention, from conflict management to conflict transformation, from restorative justice to peacekeeping” (Wani, 2011, p. 109). Akinola & Uzodike (2017, p. 95) attempted to relate the concept of *Ubuntu*, “an African humanist ideology,” with the pursuit for conflict resolution in Africa. These scholars conclude that observance of the philosophies of *Ubuntu* by state and non-state actors would significantly lessen threats to peace and security in Africa.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Deng & Lin (2022, p. 81) defined Artificial Intelligence (AI) as “a branch of computer science that focuses on creating intelligent machines that can think and act like humans.” In the words of Limna, et al. (2023, p. 65),

The origins of AI and chatbots can be traced back to the 1950s when scientists first began exploring artificial intelligence.... The early developments of AI included the creation of the first AI program called ELIZA, which aimed to replicate human conversation. Over time, AI technology progressed and led to the development of more advanced chatbots that can understand and respond to complex requests. Today, chatbots and AI are utilised in numerous industries, from healthcare to customer service, continuously advancing as technology progresses.

Little will be said in this paper since the paper does not aim generally at Artificial Intelligence (AI), but at ChatGPT which is a natural language processing (NLP) – a type of machine learning system.

ChatGPT

GPT (that fully means Generative Pre-trained Transformer) – an artificial intelligence (AI) model – was released by OpenAI (an American artificial intelligence research laboratory) in San Francisco, California, USA, in 2018. ChatGPT – a variant of GPT – was developed and launched on November 30, 2022, by the company (Rasul, et al., 2023, p. 2). Since then, ChatGPT has been adopted rapidly with some 100 million users in less than two months (Rasul, et al., 2023, p. 2). It is already transforming how cyberspace will look and feel to users (Ismail, 2023).

ChatGPT is an innovative technology that employs advanced artificial intelligence systems to create natural language answers to a given prompt or input (Kalla & Smith, 2023). ChatGPT is a sibling model to InstructGPT – another artificial intelligence (AI) tool – that can interact conventionally (OpenAI, 2023). Gill & Kaur (2023, p. 262) described ChatGPT as “a robust NLP [that is, natural language processing] model that can comprehend and create natural language for a wide range of applications, including text production, language understanding, and interactive programmes.” ChatGPT was described more in a blog thus: “It interacts in dialogue form and provides responses that appear surprisingly human. This language translation model also performs tasks like answering questions, providing information, and assisting with writing emails, essays, and even code!” (CloudMoyo, 2023). Shillsalot (2023) went further to say that ChatGPT can “understand and generate responses to complex queries from the user. It is a language model whose primary purpose is to generate responses like a human. Although it tries to be accurate, the user must verify the information

it generates, because the bot is 100% accurate. It merely mimics a human.” According to Deng & Lin (2022, p, 82),

ChatGPT has several features that make it a powerful NLP system. It is able to understand the context of a conversation and generate appropriate responses. It can also generate responses in multiple languages, including English, Spanish, French, and German. Additionally, ChatGPT is able to generate responses in different styles, such as formal, informal, and humorous.

ChatGPT and Conflict Resolution

Technological tools have had great influences on conflict resolution in recent times. So, it would not be strange that AI tools in general and ChatGPT in particular have started having impacts on means of conflict resolution. Salger (2023) asserted, “Artificial Intelligence technology such as ChatGPT (GPT-3/4 Algorithm) is considered one of the most groundbreaking innovations of the last decade and has already revolutionized numerous fields, promising efficiency gains and cost reductions.” Although the “potential [of ChatGPT] for conflict resolution and peacebuilding remains largely untapped” (Frąckiewicz, 2023a), conflict resolution is taking a newer shape in this age of technology as ChatGPT is “poised to transform the field of conflict resolution” (Frąckiewicz, 2023b). This is against the backdrop, as Frąckiewicz (2023c) asserted in another place that “With the introduction of ChatGPT-4, a cutting-edge AI language model, the potential for revolutionizing conflict resolution through mediation and arbitration has become a topic of great interest.”

A scholar, in a blog, viewed the interplay between conflict resolution and Artificial Intelligence in a different dimension by asserting, “Conflict resolution is a critical aspect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as it pertains to decision-making” (AI Chat GPT, 2023). This dimension has to do with artificial agents or robots in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the human beings they are relating with. The scholar went ahead to highlight different types of conflicts in AI, methods of conflict resolution in AI, benefits of using conflict resolution strategies in AI, challenges in implementing AI conflict resolution, examining three approaches to AI conflict resolution, potential applications of AI conflict resolution and concluded that “When creating artificial intelligence systems, it is important to consider conflict resolution strategies before implementation. Conflict resolution strategies mitigate the risks associated with AI systems and play an important role in ensuring they operate ethically when making decisions” (AI Chat GPT, 2023). Undoubtedly, this dimension calls for further study.

In a paper presented by Bognár (2019) in a conference, the scholar highlighted the impacts of technology in general and AI in particular on conflict resolution. The scholar traced the history of these impacts from traditional alternative dispute resolution (ADR) (or traditional mediation) where only people were involved to online dispute resolution (ODR) (or E-mediation/online mediation) where technologies or electronic communication channels were employed, digital courts to courts of AI where AI makes “a decision and settle our conflicts.” This may sound unbelievable according to the scholar. However, ChatGPT is making this to be more realistic than it used to be some years back when the scholar presented the paper.

Courts of AI have led to what is now known as an “Alternative Dispute Resolution system utilizing AI (AIDR)” (Abbott & Elliott, n.d., p. 2). This system has “come a long way since these applications, and demand has increased recently due to the COVID-19 pandemic that

restricted travel and face-to-face interaction” was explained better by Abbott & Elliott (n.d., p. 3).

Storytelling has been identified as one of the processes of resolving conflicts, especially through mediation (Afolaranmi, 2021, p. 12). Interestingly, one can use ChatGPT to develop a story. This is enumerated in an article published online recently (Wolfe, 2023). This can be done by setting the premise, generating a theme, creating the characters, picking a point of view, setting the setting, forming the tone, deciding on the conflict, and choosing the resolution (Wolfe, 2023). If ChatGPT can be used to develop a story in resolving a conflict as Wolfe (2023) has demonstrated, if it is research into, is experimented, the AI tool can be used in other forms of conflict resolution.

There are many seeming advantages of ChatGPT. These include reducing time and effort for tasks that previously took hours, easing to use with no or little training, speed and efficiency in performance, cost-effectiveness, personalization, and analytics (CloudMoyo, 2023). As said by Ivankov (2023), the advantages of ChatGPT include imitation of human conversation, building based on an advanced GPT model, expansive applications and benefits, availability of plugins for extension, and openness for further fine-tuning. All these advantages are a plus to conflict resolution if ChatGPT is employed in resolving conflicts. However, ChatGPT has some disadvantages that experts in conflict resolution should be careful of. These include a lack of emotional intelligence, limited context and knowledge, security risks, inexperience because ChatGPT is still in its developmental stages, and technical hitches (CloudMoyo, 2023). Ivankov (2023) added other disadvantages thus, inaccuracies and ambiguities, limited knowledge of recent events, ethical issues and concerns, and other possible legal implications. Some people have even seen ChatGPT as “a perfect tool for disinformation” and thereby poses a “fascinating problem” (Gill, 2023, p. 11).

Despite the glaring disadvantages of ChatGPT, someone has posited that Artificial Intelligence (AI) could assist alleviate some obstacles of human error in improving the probabilities of peace (Verdict, 2023). This can be achieved if people take an optimistic view of technology and see how to manoeuvre over the disadvantages. The benefits of this newest technology should make peacebuilders find ways to utilize it more in their operations. After considering many factors between Human Political Intelligence (PI) or simply Human Intelligence (HI) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) regarding conflicts and violence in the world, Oberg (2023) concluded that “...it is a mind-boggling thought – that it would be better for the world if AI were used as an *inspirational* tool in conflict resolution and peace-making policies than if we continue to rely completely on the HI-Human Intelligence, which presently dominates in prime ministers’ offices, defence, foreign ministries and parliaments.”

Furthermore, it has been noted that “AI technologies could be harnessed for long-term peacebuilding in three potential areas” (Verdict, 2023). These areas are:

- First, it can provide comprehensive legal analysis, ensuring all international and national laws are respected and applied for an effective Rule of Law to maintain stability in society in the short and long term.
- Second, it can support accountability mechanisms by gathering evidence of mass atrocities, which often take place in environments that are tough for humans to identify information in. Victims of war crimes and crimes against humanity can use this information to obtain justice, allowing society to begin the healing processes and work towards a prosperous future.

- Third, the Founding Director of the Diplo Foundation has argued that “bottom-up AI” (such as LLMs or other machine learning) can foster an inclusive, innovative, and democratic society—an environment symbiotic with peace (Verdict, 2023).

Conclusions and Recommendations

In the course of carrying out this review, this researcher found out that some researchers have started researching the influence of ChatGPT on learning and academic activities. However, many experts in peace study and conflict resolution have not written on the impacts of emerging technology on peace study and conflict resolution. These experts should start focusing on this topic and come up with scholarly written articles that will help peace study and conflict resolution practitioners in using the technology in their practice. This paper should serve as an eye-opener for researchers to study further the relationship between the two concepts. Against the backdrop that ChatGPT has many advantages that people in other professions have been making use of, experts, scholars, and other stakeholders in peace study and conflict resolution should harness the opportunities that the newest AI tool offers in their operations. This will likely improve conflict resolution and promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development and thereby making Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations more achievable before the year 2030.

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